

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF MILK AND DAIRY PRODUCTS.

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ABSTRACT

More than just milk to improve farm profitability and profitability sale as raw materials, as well as from farms and milk processing From dairy production, no matter the size, it's a job how complex and to a certain extent expensive, requires special knowledge it depends. The history of dairy farming is a major specialty.

paving the way for fully automated dairy plants passes. The situation in recent years shows that farms and specialized modules and low power for personal plots factories have been created and the production of dairy products is traditional accepts. Industrial milk processing in the agro-industrial complex. Increasing efficiency, especially in a market economy, its based on the complete and rational use of all components.

Involving Boris in a holding based on the principles of waste-free technologies So, the scene. Secondary products in the dairy processing process - skim milk, whey and whey, which are secondary considered raw food. Small business professionals are recycled materials. rational use of food, food, food, Production of medical preparations and technical semi-finished products must be organized.

As of October 1, 2023, the number of cattle raised in all categories of farms in Uzbekistan reached 13.9 million heads. The Statistics Agency reports this. This figure increased by 2% compared to the corresponding period in 2022. Analysis by economic categories shows that 91.3% of the total number of cattle were owned by farmers and household plots, 7% - in farms, 1.7% - in organizations engaged in agricultural activities.

Relevance of the problem. In the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2009, there were 180.2 thousand cows. Gross milk production was 278 thousand tons, and the republic met the needs of its population for dairy products by 70-80% from its own milk, and in 2005 the number of cows amounted to 6 million 571.8 thousand heads, 160 thousand were produced. tons (43%).

At the same time, in the summer months, 60-70% of the annual volume of milk is

milking, a significant part of which is in remote areas that do not have good transport connections or electricity supply. Under such conditions, milk is only processed into butter.

This milk processing scheme leads to large losses and losses of dairy products, since 50-60% of secondary raw materials (SRR) - skim milk, buttermilk, whey - is not used for human nutrition and is poured out or used to feed livestock. Thus, a huge amount of milk protein, carbohydrate raw materials (MBUS) with a high content of vitamins, minerals and other valuable nutrients is thrown away.

This situation with local milk production and processing is also associated with the poor state of the material and technical base.

So, in 2001, at the existing 340 milk processing facilities, the wear and tear of technological equipment amounted to 75%. Almost all existing buildings, as well as technological equipment, did not meet the requirements for the production of high-quality competitive dairy products

Taking this into account, the Presidential program for the socio-economic development of villages in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2018 set important tasks for the technical re-equipment of milk production and processing.

The creation of modern milk processing enterprises will determine the main directions in the development of milk processing in rural areas, the creation of budget-generating enterprises with a high standard of production and, on this basis, the production of a wide range of high-quality, environmentally friendly competitive dairy products from local raw materials. This will reduce the import of dairy products, increase the flow of income to the local budget, and create additional jobs, which will have a beneficial effect on the employment of the rural population.

Goals and objectives of research. The purpose of the research is to study the state of production, milk processing and develop ways to develop the processing industry in the Republic In accordance with the goal, the objectives of the study included:

- study the state of milk production and processing in the republic;
- to develop the scientific and technological foundations of industrial milk processing technology based on the creation of milk processing enterprises.
- state of milk production and processing;

Scientific novelty. Taking into account the regional natural and economic conditions of Uzbekistan, the scientific and technological foundations for the creation of modern milk processing enterprises have been developed, allowing for the introduction of the production of high-quality, environmentally friendly, competitive dairy products from local raw materials.

Practical value. The creation of processing enterprises in rural areas stimulates the growth of milk production, which leads to an increase in the profitability of rural production, the creation of additional jobs, an influx of funds into the local budget, and the supply of natural dairy products to agriculture. provides the population.

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